

THE IMPACT OF OXIDATION INHIBITORS ON BRITTLE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Oxidation protection efforts directly impact the mechanics and performance of high temperature brittle composites. The protection is usually in the form of a multi-layer external coating. In order to provide additional protection internally, recent developments have led to dispersing rigid particles within the layers through the thickness of the laminate. At high temperatures and in the presence of oxygen that may have penetrated the external coating, these particles react with the oxygen to form an internal glassy sealant. Thus the oxidation resistance is provided with two different techniques which complicate the mechanical analysis necessary to assess the performance of a laminate. The change in laminate response, i.e., constitutive behavior, is dependent on temperature, chemical reaction rates, the distribution of defects, cracks, porosity, and time. Our primary goal is to couple thermal and chemical kinetics to laminate mechanics. These issues will be addressed for coated carbon-carbon (C-C) with boron carbide as the particulate inhibitor. A simplified computational model of an orthotropic medium with a rigid inclusion possessing temperature dependent material properties is presented.

INTRODUCTION

Brittle composites such as carbon fiber/carbon matrix (C-C) composites are excellent candidates for many high temperature structural applications. These materials have been shown to maintain their strength in inert environments to about 2000 °C (3632 °F) [1]. However, in oxygen rich environments above 500 °C (932 °F), C-C composites oxidize rapidly. A standard method of protecting carbon-carbon from oxidation is through the use of external oxidation barrier coatings. Coating systems range from simple single layer coatings to more advanced multi-layer systems. Common coating materials are silicon based such as silicon carbide or silicon nitride. In these multi-layer coating systems, a dense layer of silicon carbide or silicon nitride is placed over a dense layer of boron carbide. Cracks and defects in the outer coating are sealed by the borate glass formed by the oxidation of the boron carbide sub-layer [2]. Cracks form in the coating due to the different rates of thermal expansion between the coating and substrate and serve as oxygen paths to the underlying structure. As a result, barrier coatings cannot serve as the sole protection

component in an effective oxidation protection system (OPS) [3]. In order to increase the overall effectiveness of the OPS, internal, particulate, oxidation inhibitors are considered as an auxiliary defense against oxidation. Upon exposure to oxygen at elevated temperatures, these particles will form glasses that will serve as an internal sealant and provide in-depth oxidation protection [4]. Figure 1 shows a through-the-thickness view of a matrix inhibited 2-D, 8 harness satin weave carbon-carbon laminate. The inhibitor materials in this case include a combination of boron carbide, silicon carbide and zirconium diboride. This micrograph was taken before oxidation. Note that the distribution of the inhibitor particles is concentrated near the cross-over regions of the weave architecture.

Figure 1 - Through-the-Thickness View of a Matrix Inhibited C-C Laminate

Current methods used to evaluate the effectiveness of an oxidation protection system focus on the weight loss of the material during oxidation. Therefore, these methods yield little insight into the internal mechanisms involved in oxidation and their impact on laminate mechanics. In order to develop efficient numerical models of oxidation resistant carbon-carbon, it is necessary to couple the chemical kinetics and temperature dependence of the OPS with the conventional mechanics of 2-D woven materials. A simple finite element model was utilized to study the effects of incorporating phase changing inclusions in a material. This approach is presented in the following section.

NUMERICAL MODELS

The goal of the current research effort is to develop numerical models that will allow for the mechanical characterization of oxidation resistant carbon-carbon materials. Parameters associated with the textile architecture of woven laminates, such as the statistical distribution of crossover debonds, voids, crimp angles and weave misalignment angles, become quite important in

providing statistical substantiation of processing defects. These parameters are influenced greatly by the processing environment of the material and have been shown to have a profound effect on mechanical performance.

Ochoa, et al. [5] developed an in-plane unit cell finite element representation of uninhibited, 2-D, 8 harness satin weave, C-C laminates. Since these numerical models were developed for uninhibited carbon-carbon laminates, they do not account for the presence of particulate oxidation inhibitors. The current research effort focuses on further developing these existing models to account for the oxidation protection system. In order to understand the temperature dependent phase change of a material and its effect on the surrounding medium, two simple finite element models are undertaken. A schematic representation of the inclusion models is shown in Figure 2. These models are used to investigate the thermal as well as the thermomechanical response of the system. The thermal response of the model is studied by applying a uniform temperature load ranging from 24 °C (75 °F) to 1093 °C (1500 °F). In order to investigate the thermomechanical response, a unit displacement is applied to all nodes along the rightmost boundary of model 1. In each case, the inhibitor is modeled as an isotropic material with temperature dependent material properties to account for the phase transformation. The inhibitor material properties vary from that of boron carbide at 24 °C (75 °F) [$E = 64.5$ Msi, $\nu = 0.17$, $\alpha = 2.78 \times 10^{-6}$ /°F] to those of ambient temperature B₂O₃ glass at a model temperature of 1093 °C (2000 °F) [$E = 3.3129$ Msi, $\nu = 0.2$, $\alpha = 7.83 \times 10^{-6}$ /°F]. The inclusion properties at the intermediate temperatures are assigned by linear interpolation. The properties of the orthotropic region represent a typical balanced, woven, carbon-carbon medium [$E_{11} = E_{22} = 14.1$ Msi, $G_{12} = 1.3$ Msi, $\nu_{12} = 0.01$, $\alpha_{11} = 0.24 \times 10^{-6}$ /°F, $\alpha_{22} = 0.26 \times 10^{-6}$ /°F]. Due to the symmetry of a circular inclusion in a square medium, a quarter model finite element model is used. Symmetry displacement boundary conditions were used along the edges shown in Figure 2. Three noded, triangular and four noded, quadrilateral plane stress elements with 2 in-plane displacements per node were used throughout each of the models.

Figure 2 - Schematic of Finite Element Inclusion Model

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evolution of the stress field with temperature due to the different rates of thermal expansion between the inclusion and C-C medium was investigated for temperatures ranging from an ambient temperature of 24 °C (75 °F) to 1093 °C (2000 °F). The stress versus temperature distribution is presented at a single element within the inclusion (element 72) and a single element outside the inclusion (element 304). Also, only the values for σ_x are presented. The normal stress in the y-direction (σ_y) was investigated and had a similar variation with temperature as σ_x . The magnitude of σ_y varied slightly from the σ_x stress due to the slight difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion assumed for the y-direction of the C-C region. Figure 3 shows the stress versus temperature behavior within the inclusion and outside the inclusion for model 1. Figure 4 shows the change in σ_x as a function of position along the radial line R in Figure 2 for model 1. In each case note that the magnitude of the stress incurred is decreased as the distance from the inclusion is increased.

Figure 3 - σ_x Variation with Temperature for Elements 72 and 304 of Model 1

Figure 4 - σ_x Variation with Position for Model 1

Model 2 is used to investigate the thermomechanical response of the inclusion model. As noted in Figure 2, a larger inclusion is incorporated into this model. The volume fraction of the inclusion for model 2 is about 15 % as compared to about 1% for model 1. The larger volume fraction is representative of the particulate inhibitor volume fractions common to oxidation resistant C-C materials. In addition to being subjected to an identical temperature load as that applied to model 1, model 2 is also subjected a mechanical loading along the rightmost boundary. The mechanical load is in the form of a unit displacement applied at each of the nodes along the boundary. Figure 5 represents the global stress versus strain response for model 2. The stresses are calculated using the average of the reaction forces distributed over boundary surface area. The strains are the average of the nodal values along the boundary. In order to present realistic stress and strain values for a carbon-carbon medium, it was necessary to truncate the stress vs. strain data shown in Figure 5. As a result, Figure 5 does not represent the global stress strain response for the entire load case. The data was truncated above 538 °C (1000 °F). Since the material properties are assigned by linear interpolation at a given temperature, the complete transformation of the inclusion properties is not complete at the point where the data is truncated. The inclusion has a Young's modulus of 35.1 Msi at this intermediate temperature. As indicated in Figure 5, the presence of a phase changing inclusion has little effect on the global thermomechanical response of the system. An interesting point to note in Figure 5 is that the model with the softening inclusion appears to have the lowest global stiffness even though the inclusion modulus remains greater than the modulus of the surrounding C-C region for the entire temperature range plotted. This may be due to the large thermal mismatch between the inclusion and surrounding C-C substrate. Initially, the thermal expansion coefficient of the inhibitor particle is approximately 10 times that of the carbon-carbon region. The large expansion in the inclusion region may account for the reduced stiffness in the inclusion model. Additionally, effects such as local element failure in the region of the inclusion are not accounted for in these models. Element failure in the region and the corresponding stress redistribution may effect the global thermomechanical response of the system. A damage routine to address the effects of localized element failure will be included in future modeling attempts.

Figure 5 - Global Stress vs. Strain Response for Model 2

In each of the previously discussed models, the inclusion is constrained from free expansion by the surrounding carbon substrate. However, carbon-carbon is a porous material. Therefore, the thermal expansion of the inclusion may be less restricted by the surrounding carbon. The effect of a porous region on the stress field in and around the inclusion was studied by introducing a ring of porous material around the inhibitor particle of Figure 2. The elastic properties of the material were assumed to be isotropic and very low in magnitude [$E = 0.001 \text{ MI}$, $\nu = 0.2$]. In this situation, all of the stresses in the body were relieved to negligible values. However, in this model, all of the porous material in the body was assumed to be concentrated directly around the particle. In reality there is a statistical distribution of the pores throughout the body. This distribution of pores will undoubtedly permit a somewhat less restricted expansion of the particulate. As a result, the stresses may not be as large as those predicted by the simplified models mentioned above. Also, as shown in Figure 1, the inclusion particles typically concentrate in loosely packed clusters. The loose packing of the particles may also serve to ease the restriction on the expansion of the inhibitor particles during the phase transformation. In addition, the liquid state of the internal glasses at oxidation critical temperatures may cause further stress relaxation due to viscoelastic effects.

CONCLUSIONS

An initial simplified approach to evaluate the effect of a phase changing inclusion in an orthotropic media was undertaken in order to simulate particulate inhibitors in brittle composites. The phase transformation of the inclusion particle has little effect on the global stress strain response of the current models. However, it should be noted that the local effects around the inclusion are significant. Therefore, future modeling attempts will focus on the boundary region between the inclusion and substrate to capture the interaction and its effect on the global thermomechanical response. The modeling approach employed several simplifications. The

transition of the inclusion into borate glass will be accompanied by a large volume expansion. This aspect of the transformation is not accounted for in the present modeling attempts. The presence of porosity throughout the body also effects the internal stress caused by the oxidation of the inhibitors. Therefore homogenization theories will be of critical importance in incorporating the distributions of the pores and other internal defects into the unit cell finite element model mentioned herein. All of these factors are presently being investigated in order to more accurately model the response of oxidation resistant carbon-carbon laminates.

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